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Lost in Translation? Not for Large Language Models:

Automated Divergent Thinking Scoring Performance Translates to Non-English Contexts

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Abstract

Divergent thinking (DT) has been at the heart of creativity measurement for over seven decades. At the same time, large-scale usage of DT tests is limited due to the tedious procedure of scoring the responses, which often requires several judges to assess thousands of participants' ideas. Across two studies (N = 195 and N = 404), we examined the quality of artificial intelligence-based scoring models (*Ocsai, Organisciak et al., 2023*) to score Alternate Uses Tasks (Study 1: brick, Study 2: brick, can, rope). Based on more than 6000 ideas provided by participants in Polish and automatically translated to English, we fit a series of idea (response)- and prompt (object)-level structural equation models. When artificial intelligence-based and semantic distance scores were modeled together, latent correlations with human ratings ranged from $r = .56$ to $r = .95$ at the response (idea) level and from $r = .61$ to $r = .99$ at the object (prompt) level. A hierarchical (i.e., person-level) model with three DT tasks modeled together (Study 2) demonstrated a latent correlation between automatized and human ratings of $r = .96$ (*Babbage*) and $r = .98$ (*DaVinci*). Notably, the same results were obtained based on untranslated responses provided in Polish. Automated and human scores provided the same serial-order effect pattern and the same profile of differences under "be fluent" vs. "be creative" instructions. This investigation offers an initial yet compelling argument that the new algorithms provide a close-to-perfect score of DT tasks when benchmarked against human ratings, even when the responses are created in a different language and automatically translated to English or used in an untranslated form.

Keywords: Divergent Thinking; Alternate Uses Task; Assessment; GPT-3; Babbage; DaVinci

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Since the early works of the founders of creativity science (Guilford, 1956, 1967; Torrance, 1972), creativity scholars have relied heavily on divergent thinking (DT) tasks. This is not surprising: although DT has been criticized (Baer, 2011; Hocevar, 1981), it is not controversial to consider it a valuable proxy of creative potential (Runco & Acar, 2012), particularly because it predicts creative accomplishments relatively well (Lebuda et al., 2021; Plucker, 1999; Said-Metwaly et al., 2022; Zaccaro et al., 2015).

DT denotes people's ability to provide multiple, various, and original ideas or problem solutions. DT tasks' results are usually operationalized and scored in terms of fluency (the number of ideas provided), flexibility (the number of distinct categories the response can be classified to, Guilford, 1967; or the number of switches between ideas: Acar & Runco, 2017; Mastria et al., 2021), and originality (the rarity of the responses, Runco, 2008; or their cleverness and uncommonness, Wilson et al., 1953). DT correlates quite robustly with intelligence (up to $r = .37$; Gerwig et al., 2021), particularly its broad retrieval ability (*Gr*) factor ($r = .48$; Miroshnik et al., 2023). Another well-replicated finding in the creativity literature is that people obtain more original responses with time (i.e., subsequent ideas are more original than previous ones: a serial order effect: Beaty & Silvia, 2012; Christensen et al., 1957) and that originality of DT responses grow if people are explicitly asked to be creative or original (as opposed to "be fluent" instruction: Acar et al., 2020; Dumas et al., 2021; Harrington, 1975; Nusbaum et al., 2014; Said-Metwaly et al., 2020).

Scoring DT tasks is challenging. The most straightforward DT aspect to score is fluency, as it denotes the raw number of adequate responses provided. The problem, however, is that fluency alone is loosely related to the very definition of creativity, which sees original and useful ideas as creative (Runco & Jaeger, 2012; Stein, 1953). Being fluent means being generative or productive—entities that certainly play a role in real-world creativity (Forthmann & Dumas, 2022) yet are not

synonymous with it (Zeng et al., 2011). Sometimes fluency is treated as a proxy of creativity (Turner, 1999), mainly because of high correlations with flexibility and originality. Moreover, high fluency might increase the likelihood of finding original ideas, as asserted by the “extended effort principle” (Parnes, 1961). However, it is well-established that strong correlations are observed only when summative scoring of originality is used, i.e., when it is calculated based on the sums of the originality of responses provided. This fluency contamination effect (Clark & Mirels, 1970; Hocevar, 1979) disappears when other ways of scoring are used (e.g., top-scoring, snapshot scoring, etc.; Forthmann, Szardenings et al., 2020; Silvia et al., 2008).

Thus, creativity researchers have become more interested in scoring the flexibility or originality of the responses provided. Yet the problem with flexibility is also quite apparent—the number of categories or switches between ideas is a function of the number of responses. Thus, flexibility is also driven by fluency (and this confound is even more apparent between fluency and flexibility than when fluency and originality are considered; see Acar et al., 2022). And while flexibility better than fluency fits the definition of divergent thinking, it does not necessarily match the definition of creativity. In some models, flexibility is theorized as a vital mechanism of creative thought (Nijstad et al., 2010), but it is unclear whether flexibility scores bring additional value over fluency and originality (Weiss & Wilhelm, 2022).

Consequently, originality is the most often scored and analyzed aspect of divergent thinking. It comes as no surprise, given that originality is central to both scholarly (Runco & Jaeger, 2012) and naïve definitions of creativity (Gralewski, 2019; Gralewski & Karwowski, 2018; Spiel & von Korff, 1998). The two most often used approaches to assess originality are based on either statistical infrequency or subjective scoring. Rarity (i.e., infrequency) scores are perceived to be more objective than subjective scoring (Runco, 2008), but recent works (Forthmann et al., 2021; Forthmann, Paek, et al., 2020) demonstrated that scores’ reliability depends on the sample size and the number of ideas generated (i.e., fluency). More specifically, studies on adults (Forthmann, Paek, et al., 2020) and children (Forthmann et al., 2021) have found that when the sample is small and the number of ideas

each person provided is limited, originality scores tend to be severely unreliable. Moreover, statistical rarity alone is insufficient as it might result in nonsensical ideas being scored as original, as they're indeed rare (Forthmann & Doebler, 2022).

Subjective scoring, particularly when coders are trained and provided with a detailed description of what counts as original or creative (e.g., Silvia et al., 2008), offers a vital alternative for rarity scoring. Although there is no gold standard regarding the number of judges, their training, and detailed information provided (and such a standard would be worthwhile, see Reiter-Palmon et al., 2019), and substantial variability between labs exists, some similarities are worth noting. In short, across several investigations, scholars adapted the procedure outlined in Silvia et al. (2008), i.e., by providing their coders with the classical indicators of originality and brief training, using 4 or 5 Likert scales (see, e.g., Benedek & Zöhrer, 2020) and relying on latent variable modeling to obtain the scores (Forthmann, Jendryczko, et al., 2019; Karwowski et al., 2020).

Still, the problems with a broader application of DT tasks are primarily associated with how time- and effort-consuming scoring procedures are. Nowadays, researchers' striving for greater statistical power and the greater availability of online studies have resulted in a much larger sample size than in earlier studies. Additionally, there is a shared agreement that several DT tasks should be used to control for the task's solution space (Beaty et al., 2022; Forthmann, Paek, et al., 2020; Hass, 2017), which creates a greater effort to score the responses. Consider a sample of 800 participants who solve five divergent thinking tasks. Assuming an average of 7 responses per task per person, this would result in almost 30 thousand ideas to score. What about even bigger samples in extensive educational or cross-cultural studies? The scoring quickly becomes a nightmare, making many scholars hesitant to include DT tasks in their batteries. Moreover, manual scoring methods—whether reliant on subjective ratings or infrequency—are hardly sustainable. Coders frequently require training for each task, and given that the role is typically filled by graduate students, there is an inevitable turnover necessitating recurrent training. Fortunately, technology might help creativity scholars score DT tasks quickly and effectively. In what follows, we briefly describe the recent

advances in automated scoring of DT tasks (and other creativity tasks more generally) and present the results of two studies that assess the effectiveness of the newly created algorithms to score DT.

Automated Scoring of DT

Automated scoring is all but new. Rediscovered recently (Forthmann & Doebler, 2022), an early but overlooked approach to using automated scoring of Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking was introduced in the late sixties (Paulus et al., 1970; Paulus & Renzuli, 1968), and it keeps working well also today. This approach—using stylometric characteristics of the responses provided (e.g., number of words, commas, periods, or question marks) to estimate originality—is the first successful attempt to go beyond relying exclusively on human raters in scoring DT.

Given the intensive development of automated scoring in the last two decades and the various solutions proposed, different categorizations of these approaches are possible. Chronologically first approaches used the semantic distance between the target participant was provided with (e.g., “a brick” or “a can” in a typical AUT task) and the participants’ responses (Dumas & Dunbar, 2014; Dunbar & Forster, 2009). Semantic vector models based on Latent Semantic Analysis (Landauer et al., 1998), Word2Vec (Mikolov et al., 2013), or GloVe (Pennington et al., 2014) were used to score the originality of DT task responses when compared to a target word; using cosine distance, they would literally measure the divergence between prompt and response. While early attempts suffered from some limitations (e.g., elaboration bias—with the more elaborated response provided by the participant, latent distance scored were higher, Forthmann, Oyebade, et al., 2019), newer models (Beaty et al., 2022; Yu et al., 2022) quite effectively resolved this problem, providing impressive correlations between automated scores and human raters (e.g., latent correlations of $r = .75$ and $r = .91$ achieved at the participant level, without controlling for fluency, in recent studies, Beaty & Johnson, 2021). An extension of latent semantic models to score the originality of divergent thinking tasks in 12 languages (Patterson et al., in press) used maximum associative distance (Yu et al., 2022) between a target and all words in response as a way to limit or eliminate the elaboration bias. It demonstrated moderate to large correlations (r s between .23 and

.52 at the person level) with human raters, with quite high heterogeneity between languages, implying that this method may have important limitations when used with languages other than English, and especially for those languages that use alphabets other than the Roman alphabet (i.e., Hebrew). Further, the effectiveness of semantic vector models is much noisier at the response level, especially in cases where validation data is held-out for model testing. An evaluation of popular semantic distance systems from Beaty and Johnson (SemDis; 2021) and Dumas et al. (OCS; 2020) against data from nine prior studies found weak to low correlation with human judgments ($r = .12$ for SemDis to $r = .26$ for OCS, respectively; Organisciak et al. 2023).

Supervised machine learning models, where models are taught based on prior data, include a variety of approaches (see, e.g., Buczak et al., 2022; or Organisciak et al., 2023, for a comprehensive discussion of differences between supervised and unsupervised machine learning models in creativity scoring). Paulus's (Paulus et al., 1970; Paulus & Renzuli, 1968) early approach is an example of a supervised model as properties of participants' responses were first used to predict originality scores (human ratings) in a subsample of cases (training phase), and then identified predictors were applied in the cross-validation and testing phases. As Forthmann and Doebler (2022) demonstrated, this solution yielded robust latent person-level correlations with human raters ($r = .59$).

A recent example of supervised machine learning was presented by Organisciak et al. (2023), who adopted a process called *transfer learning* to an emerging class of large language models. They fine-tuned a pre-trained model on divergent thinking test responses scored by human judges, adapting it to the problem space. Large language models do not formally focus on semantic distances between the solution's words, and instead try to learn meaningful—though more opaque—patterns from their training data in extremely large forms of a neural network known as a Transformer (Vaswani et al., 2017). As Organisciak et al. (2023) showed, their solution resulted in impressive correlations on nine large databases. The best system, trained on the Generative Pre-trained Transformer 3 architecture (GPT-3) and called Ocsai (*Open Creativity Scoring with Artificial Intelligence*) henceforth, showed an average correlation of $r = .81$ with human judges on the direct

responses. Although the performance of GPT-3 solutions differed across the algorithms used and the tasks scored, in all cases it resulted in much higher correlations with human raters than correlations between semantic distances and raters, treated as a baseline. Importantly, Ocsai scores were highly similar to human raters in the case of prompts that the algorithm was not trained on ($r_s > .60$). There are exciting consequences of this solution, as it might potentially make divergent thinking tasks much more often and easily used.

In this study, we examine the effectiveness of Organisciak and colleagues' approach when applied to responses provided in a language other than English (Polish in the case of this paper) and automatically translated, as well as when used in a raw, untranslated form. Thus, we examine if the model is able to effectively score creativity of responses provided in a different language than it was trained on. Moreover, we test if automated scores follow the same validity patterns as human ratings. Two specific aspects of validity we are interested in are the serial order effect (Beaty & Silvia, 2012; Christensen et al., 1957) and the "be creative" instruction effect (Harrington, 1975).

To conclude, although attempts to provide automated scoring of divergent thinking have been around for more than half of a century, automated scoring of creativity has a long yet short history. Paulus approach, rediscovered and reapplied recently, is still effective. Semantic distance solutions, particularly enriched by recent algorithms (Dumas et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2022), are promising, yet a fascinating new route for creativity research involves large language models artificial intelligence-based solutions that outperform more traditional semantic distance-based scores, mainly when aggregated across responses and tasks and modeled at a person level.

At the same time, we note that most studies conducted so far focused on scoring verbal divergent thinking tasks, mostly AUT. Exceptions worth highlighting are recent attempts to use automated methods to score the creativity of short stories (Johnson et al., 2021) based on several algorithms that were highly effective in resembling human raters' scores ($r = .77$: Study 1, and the latent correlation between automated and human ratings, $r = .85$). Less developed are algorithms that score figural tasks, like TTCT-figural, Test of Creative Thinking-Drawing Production (Jellen &

Urban, 1986), or Test of Creative Imagery Abilities (Jankowska & Karwowski, 2015). On a small sample of drawings, AI-based models effectively recognized and categorized drawings as more and less creative (Cropley & Marrone, 2022), resembling human raters' scores. A recent Automatic Drawing Assessment (AuDrA) platform (Patterson et al., 2022) used models that were pre-trained and validated on a sample of over 13000 drawings from the Multi-Trial Creative Ideation task (MTCI; Barbot, 2018). Correlations with human raters for different drawings generated in response to the cues the algorithm was trained on resulted in an impressive correlation of $r = .81$, yet there was a lower transferability to other tasks ($r = .47$). Importantly, AuDrA's originality scores were found not to be seriously inflated by elaboration.

The Present Studies

Across two studies ($N = 195$ and $N = 404$, 6121 ideas overall), we tested how effective AI-based algorithms (GPT-3) are in scoring DT tasks when responses are provided in another language than English (here: Polish) and either automatically translated to English for AI-based scoring of originality or used in an original, untranslated, form. A previous investigation (Organisciak et al., 2023) demonstrated high correlations between human and AI ratings when responses were provided in English (r s up to $.81$). This study extends previous research in two ways. First, we are interested in replicating the patterns when responses are provided in a language other than English and then automatically translated to English or used untranslated. Second, we test some additional validity measures of AI scores: we check if automated scores resemble human ratings in terms of the serial order effect (i.e., whether the later ideas are more original than the initial ones; see Acar & Runco, 2014 for a similar approach) and whether AI and human ratings show the same differences between "be fluent" and "be creative" conditions.

Method

Participants and Procedure

The datasets used in this investigation come from two online studies. Participants from Study 1 were $N = 195$ Polish adults (50% female) aged 18-58 ($M = 24.25$, $SD = 6.66$) recruited from the

Prolific research panel. Study 2 included N = 404 Poles (50% female) aged 19-44 (M = 31.56, SD = 6.92), members of the Syno International panel. Both studies were conducted as part of larger research projects that required participants to complete several self-report scales and performance tasks, including the Alternate Uses Task (AUT).

In Study 1, we administered AUT with the “be creative” instruction. In Study 2, we randomly assigned participants to either “be creative” or “be fluent” condition. In both studies, participants were Poles, so AUT prompts and responses were provided in Polish. Study 1 utilized one AUT prompt: a brick (“cegła” in Polish), and Study 2 used three prompts: a brick, a can (“puszka”), and rope¹ (“sznurek”). A 2-minute time limit was set per each task in both studies.

Human AUT Ratings

The same three native-speaking Polish judges scored participants’ responses for originality using a 5-point scale (1 = *not original at all*, 5 = *extremely original*). The reliability of judges’ scores was moderate at the idea level (Study 1: ICC(3,1) = .58; Study 2: brick: ICC(3,1) = .64; can: ICC(3,1) = .55; rope: ICC(3,1) = .49), while at the prompt level, it ranged from good to excellent (Study 1: ICC(3,k) = .86; Study 2: brick: ICC(3,k) = .91; can: ICC(3,k) = .86; rope: ICC(3,k) = .79). The responses assessed by judges as nonsensical or the variants of “I don’t know” answers were excluded from analyses. We standardized each expert’s ratings at the idea level to control for judges’ severity (Long & Pang, 2015).

Data Preparation and Automated AUT Scoring

All 6121 generated ideas (1147 from Study 1 and 4974 from Study 2) were translated to English using two automatic translation tools: Microsoft Translator and Google Translate. Our

¹ „Sznurek” can be quite accurately translate to English also as a string or tape (see Supplementary Online Material [SOM] Table S3 for correlations between *Ocsai* scores obtained using different translations). Therefore, we checked the models with “string” and “tape” as target words, yet the results were fairly similar. At the prompt level, a latent correlation between human ratings and *Ocsai* scores estimated for “string” was at $r = .63$, 95% CI [.54, .72] (*Babbage*) and $r = .53$, 95% CI [.42, .64] (*DaVinci*). At the idea level, it was at $r = .55$, 95% CI [.50, .60] (*Babbage*) and $r = .48$, 95% CI [.43, .54] (*DaVinci*). Latent correlations between human ratings and *Ocsai* scores estimated for “tape” was at $r = .66$, 95% CI [.55, .76] (*Babbage*) and $r = .53$, 95% CI [.42, .64] (*DaVinci*) at the prompt level, and at $r = .56$, 95% CI [.51, .62] (*Babbage*) and $r = .54$, 95% CI [.48, .59] (*DaVinci*) at the idea level.

decision to use both Microsoft Translator and Google Translate was driven by a desire to capture a broader spectrum of potential translations. Given that the outputs from these tools might differ due to their distinct algorithms and data sources, using both services provided us with a more comprehensive picture of possible linguistic interpretations. While the comparison between the two translators was not our goal, we posit that their inclusion adds to the robustness of our results. On the one hand, we wanted to explore the efficiency of an approach that relies heavily on automated translation with a bare minimum of manual corrections, and uses easy and free translation services that most research labs would have easy access to. On the other, we aimed to increase the chances of preserving the original meaning of the responses. Hence, we used two translators, each with different strengths and weaknesses (e.g., our experience showed that when participants write without specific Polish letters—a common practice that results in grammatically incorrect but still comprehensible writing—Google Translate delivers more accurate results, while Microsoft Translator handles idiomatic or slang expressions better). We manually translated 653 and 52 ideas skipped by Microsoft Translator and Google Translate, respectively (e.g., due to the omitted diacritical marks or typos in Polish words).

Then, we used Generative Pre-trained Transformer 3 (GPT-3) *Ada*, *Babbage*, *Curie*, and *DaVinci* models (Organisciak et al., 2023) and the semantic distance-based originality scores (Dumas et al., 2021) from the Open Creativity Scoring (OCS) platform (<https://openscoring.du.edu/>; Organisciak & Dumas, 2020). The Ocsai system used here for LLM-based scoring was trained on a compilation of nine prior human-judged AUT datasets (Acar et al., 2023; Beaty et al., 2018; Beaty & Silvia, 2012; Dumas et al., 2021; Hofelich Mohr et al., 2016; Silvia et al., 2008, 2009, 2017). It included 27,217 responses from 2039 participants, each judged by three or more human judges, with an average random intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC2k) of .71 (Organisciak et al., 2023). Ocsai was trained on 80% of the dataset, with 5% withheld for cross-validation and 15% for evaluation. Identical responses were deduplicated from the dataset to avoid data leakage between training and test data.

Generally, Ocsai uses two large language modeling architectures: T5 (Raffel et al., 2020) and GPT-3 (Brown et al., 2020). This study used the GPT-based Ocsai models across four different model sizes, ranging from *Ada* (350M parameters), to *Babbage* (1.3B parameters), to *Curie* (6.7B parameters), to *DaVinci* (175B parameters). The scores obtained using Ocsai models range from 1 to 5, where 1 is *very unoriginal* and 5 is *very original*.

To create a comprehensive representation of automated scoring methods, we further used semantic distance methods, grounded in word corpus analysis. Despite its suboptimal performance in previous work (see, e.g., Organisciak et al., 2023), semantic distance represents an automated approach to scoring the AUT that is quite commonly employed in current research practices.

Although it may not perform at its best in isolation, we argue that incorporating semantic distance scoring alongside AI-based scores leverages their potential complementarity and thus offers a more robust depiction of the current landscape of automated scoring systems, as aimed for in our analyses. Semantic-distance-based scoring uses a continuous scale with a minimum of 0 (*totally unoriginal*) and a maximum of 2 (*very very original*), though the realistic range of values is much narrower, with 5th and 95th percentile scores of 0.65 to 0.96 for data from Dumas et al. (2021).

Analytical Approach

We took a two-step approach while analyzing our data. First, we calculated bivariate correlations between human ratings and automated scores (AI- and semantic distance-based) at the idea (response) and prompt (object) levels. Second, we selected two Ocsai models that resulted in the highest correlations between human ratings and automated scores and fitted a series of structural equation models (SEMs), again at the level of ideas and prompts. For Study 1, models (idea- and prompt-level) covered a latent factor of *machine originality* that loaded on four indices: two Ocsai scores (modeled on Microsoft Translator and Google Translate responses translated from Polish to English) and two obtained by the latent semantic distance (with estimated scores based on the same translation engines). This originality factor was correlated with a respective *human originality* factor that loaded on the three human coders' ratings.

In the case of the machine originality factor, we allowed for correlated uniqueness, i.e., the estimates based on Google and Microsoft scores covaried across Ocsai and semantic distance-based scores. This adjustment was made to account for patterns resulting from the use of the same scoring method (e.g., *DaVinci* model size) applied to both translations and the use of identical raw Polish responses to obtain outputs from different translators. These patterns might not entirely be construct-relevant, and therefore might be contained in the item-level error variance in our models. However, when misspecification issues occurred, we adjusted the models accordingly by omitting some of the assumed correlated errors (see SOM Figure S1, panel A for details). We created four models overall for Study 1: two based on the scores derived from the first selected Ocsai model and two on the scores from the second Ocsai model (each time, one estimated on the level of ideas and the other on the level of prompts). As previously noted, the selection of Ocsai model sizes was informed by their links with human ratings across datasets, with those displaying the highest correlation being chosen for SEM-based analyses.

In the case of Study 2 results, we took a similar approach, so we modeled each task at the idea and prompt level, with a latent factor of machine originality correlated with a human originality factor. Study 2 also estimated a hierarchical model with all three DT tasks loading on a higher-order originality factor in both machine and human scores (SOM Figure S1, panel B). This model should be considered a person-level model. Also, in this case, models were estimated separately for the two select Ocsai estimates that showed the highest correlation with human ratings. Additionally, we allowed the errors for human scores to correlate in the hierarchical models to account for the possible judges' bias or scoring style that would consistently manifest across tasks (objects) used.

Additionally, for both Study 1 and Study 2, we also estimated slightly different models based on untranslated input (see SOM Figure S2, for details). Specifically, we utilized raw Polish responses as input for Ocsai algorithms to investigate whether Ocsai is able of effectively score the originality of responses provided in a different language than it was trained on. For untranslated responses, we decided not to use semantic distances due to the unavailability of effective solutions (see Patterson

et al., in press, for initial results regarding the correlations between semantic distances and human-scored originality in the Polish language). Therefore, our models for automatically translated and untranslated responses had slight differences: while we incorporated semantic scores for translated input, they were omitted in the models for untranslated input. Instead, the latter contained a latent factor of machine originality that loaded on four indices: scores from *Ada*, *Babbage*, *Curie*, and *DaVinci* model sizes. In the hierarchical models ran on raw Polish responses, we correlated the errors from *Ada*, *Babbage*, *Curie*, and *DaVinci* scores to account for any systematic scoring patterns among the AI-based models.

All models were estimated in R (R Core Team, 2020) version 4.2.0 using package lavaan (Rosseel, 2012), lme4 (Bates et al., 2015), and basic R packages. Data and scripts are available in the Open Science Framework (OSF): <https://osf.io/ftnvg>.

Results

Correlations Among Measures

Descriptive statistics for scores obtained using all scoring methods employed in this study, i.e., Ocsai, semantic distance, and human ratings, are presented in SOM Tables S1-S2. Correlations between human and machine ratings of originality are presented in Table 1. In the Ocsai scores, *Ada*, *Babbage*, *Curie*, and *DaVinci* yielded comparable scores. For Ocsai estimates, the links varied between $r = .38$ (rope) and $r = .66$ (brick, Study 2) at the response (idea) level (median $r = .52$) and between $r = .46$ (rope) and $r = .82$ (brick, Study 2) at the object (prompt) level (median $r = .70$). When scores obtained in semantic distance analysis were considered, the links were visibly smaller and more heterogeneous: at the idea level, they fall between $r = .07$ (rope) and $r = .51$ (brick, Study 2) with a median of $r = .21$, and between $r = .01$ (rope) and $r = .63$ (brick, Study 2) at the prompt level, with a median of $r = .39$. As *Babbage*- and *DaVinci*-based estimates systematically showed slightly higher links with human ratings, we used them in further SEM analyses.

Table 1

Pearson's correlations between AUT manifest scores obtained using Ocsai, semantic-distance-based method, and from human judges across all datasets and prompts based on automatically translated responses

	AI (MS)	AI (Google)	Sem Distance (MS)	Sem Distance (Google)	HR
AI (MS)					
Study 1: Brick	1	.88 / .87 / .88 / .85	.35 / .34 / .32 / .27	.35 / .33 / .32 / .26	.52 / .51 / .50 / .50
Study 2: Brick	1	.83 / .86 / .81 / .84	.46 / .51 / .52 / .46	.43 / .49 / .44 / .41	.65 / .66 / .64 / .65
Study 2: Can	1	.85 / .86 / .81 / .89	.36 / .33 / .28 / .25	.33 / .33 / .32 / .31	.57 / .57 / .52 / .61
Study 2: Rope	1	.80 / .82 / .84 / .79	.32 / .29 / .35 / .26	.30 / .27 / .31 / .25	.39 / .45 / .44 / .46
AI (Google)					
Study 1: Brick	.90 / .90 / .88 / .91	1	.27 / .29 / .26 / .23	.32 / .34 / .31 / .28	.50 / .52 / .51 / .52
Study 2: Brick	.88 / .88 / .88 / .86	1	.37 / .45 / .42 / .38	.43 / .50 / .47 / .42	.61 / .65 / .63 / .64
Study 2: Can	.91 / .91 / .90 / .94	1	.20 / .22 / .18 / .18	.35 / .36 / .32 / .32	.57 / .59 / .53 / .61
Study 2: Rope	.88 / .86 / .87 / .85	1	.27 / .24 / .28 / .26	.34 / .29 / .34 / .27	.38 / .44 / .43 / .46
Sem Distance (MS)					
Study 1: Brick	.47 / .41 / .47 / .42	.36 / .36 / .36 / .37	1	.93	.23
Study 2: Brick	.54 / .65 / .60 / .58	.48 / .61 / .55 / .53	1	.90	.50
Study 2: Can	.36 / .35 / .30 / .27	.20 / .23 / .20 / .18	1	.72	.16
Study 2: Rope	.36 / .31 / .35 / .30	.30 / .23 / .31 / .32	1	.77	.05
Sem Distance (Google)					
Study 1: Brick	.49 / .41 / .48 / .45	.42 / .43 / .43 / .44	.93	1	.23
Study 2: Brick	.54 / .59 / .56 / .51	.54 / .61 / .59 / .55	.92	1	.51
Study 2: Can	.33 / .36 / .32 / .32	.30 / .32 / .30 / .28	.80	1	.19
Study 2: Rope	.33 / .27 / .32 / .26	.37 / .30 / .37 / .54	.75	1	.06
HR					
Study 1: Brick	.65 / .66 / .68 / .64	.64 / .68 / .70 / .69	.47	.47	1
Study 2: Brick	.76 / .82 / .81 / .76	.70 / .78 / .79 / .79	.63	.62	1
Study 2: Can	.75 / .73 / .66 / .74	.74 / .74 / .66 / .74	.24	.30	1
Study 2: Rope	.46 / .53 / .48 / .50	.47 / .51 / .53 / .54	.08	.08	1

Note. Prompt (object) level correlations are in the lower triangle, and idea (response) level correlations are in the upper triangle. Estimations based on the Ocsai models are separated by a slash and presented in the following order: *Ada / Babbage / Curie / DaVinci*. AI = scores obtained using the Ocsai. Sem Distance = scores obtained using the semantic-distance-based method. HR = scores averaged across three human raters. MS = Microsoft.

How effectively does the *Ocsai* perform when provided with untranslated input, i.e., prompts and responses in Polish? Apart from being trained in the English language, it did surprisingly well. As shown in Table 2, correlations between human and machine ratings of originality were robust at both idea (response) and object (prompt) levels. The *DaVinci* model displayed the highest links with human ratings. At the idea level, the correlations were estimated at $r = .42$ for both a brick (Study 1) and a rope, with even higher associations of $r = .61$ for a can, and $r = .72$ for a brick (Study 2). At the prompt level, the observed correlations ranged from $r = .55$ for a rope, to $r = .66$ for a brick (Study 1), to $r = .75$ for a can, and $r = .83$ for a brick (Study 2).

Table 2

Pearson's correlations between AUT manifest scores obtained using *Ocsai* and from human judges across all datasets and prompts for untranslated, non-English input (i.e., non-translated prompts and responses)

	Human Ratings	
	Response Level	Prompt Level
Study 1: Brick	.26 / .26 / .24 / .42	.48 / .33 / .50 / .66
Study 2: Brick	.41 / .30 / .44 / .72	.57 / .46 / .63 / .83
Study 2: Can	.31 / .46 / .53 / .61	.48 / .64 / .68 / .75
Study 2: Rope	.25 / .35 / .34 / .42	.40 / .51 / .49 / .55

Note. Estimations based on the *Ocsai* models are separated by a slash and presented in the following order: *Ada* / *Babbage* / *Curie* / *DaVinci*.

Latent Variable Modeling

SEM models generally resulted in a good to excellent fit (Hu & Bentler, 1999) (see Table 3 for fit indices), with the exception being the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), which achieved a good fit only in the hierarchical model. Latent correlations between machine and human originality scores at the idea level varied between $r = .56$ (rope, Study 2) and $r = .95$ (brick, Study 2) (median $r = .71$), while at the prompt level, they ranged from $r = .61$ (rope, Study 2) to $r = .87$ (can, Study 2), to $r = .91$ (brick, Study 1), to $r = .99$ (brick, Study 2), yielding a median $r = .92$.

When DT tasks used in Study 2 were modeled hierarchically, as a second-order, person-level originality factor, the latent correlation between machine and human ratings was $r = .96$, 95% CI: [.91, 1.00] (*Babbage*) and $r = .98$, with 95% CI: [.93, 1.00] (*DaVinci*). Thus, machine and human scores resulted in the same results when several tasks were aggregated and modeled at the person level (see the left panel in Figure 1).

SEM Models on an untranslated input

Using estimates obtained on untranslated input, we then fitted idea- and prompt-level SEM models that covered a latent factor of *machine originality* and loaded on four indices: scores from *Ada*, *Babbage*, *Curie*, and *DaVinci* models. This originality factor was correlated with a similar *human originality* factor that loaded on the three human coders' ratings. While the SEM models generally showed a good fit, we note that the RMSEA values were slightly above the typically recommended criteria (see SOM Table S4 for fit indices). Latent correlations between machine originality and human originality at the idea level ranged from $r = .52$ (brick, Study 1) to $r = .60$ (rope), to $r = .78$ (can), to $r = .83$ (brick, Study 2), yielding a median of $r = .69$. At the prompt level, latent correlations ranged from $r = .69$ (brick, Study 1) to $r = .75$ (rope), to $r = .87$ (can), to $r = .89$ (brick, Study 2), yielding a median of $r = .81$. When we modeled DT tasks used in Study 2 hierarchically, the latent correlation between machine and human ratings was $r = .99$, 95% CI: [.95, 1.00].

Table 3

SEM model fit results for each AUT prompt across both datasets (and for the hierarchical model ran on data from Study 2 only) based on automatically translated responses

Fit index	Study 1				Study 2				
	Brick		Brick		Can		Rope		Hierarchical
	Prompt-level	Idea-level	Prompt-level	Idea-level	Prompt-level	Idea-level	Prompt-level	Idea-level	Person-level
$\chi^2(df)$	46.80	131.53	29.53	247.10	60.68	251.05	60.46	185.52	469.05
	(11)***	(11)***	(11)***	(11)***	(11)***	(12)***	(12)***	(12)***	(175)***
	31.98	112.71	63.50	294.11	41.19	227.89	42.48	137.41	473.91
	(11)***	(11)***	(11)***	(11)***	(11)***	(12)***	(12)***	(12)***	(177)***
χ^2/df	4.25	11.96	2.68	22.46	5.52	20.92	5.04	15.46	2.68
	2.91	10.25	5.77	26.74	3.74	18.99	3.54	15.21	2.68
RMSEA	.133	.101	.108	.127	.136	.124	.133	.101	.076
	.105	.094	.159	.139	.108	.112	.099	.087	.075
SRMR	.020	.025	.023	.025	.031	.031	.068	.062	.119
	.021	.025	.024	.025	.031	.034	.072	.062	.122
CFI	.968	.977	.982	.967	.964	.952	.943	.961	.939
	.981	.980	.961	.960	.977	.963	.967	.970	.940
TLI	.939	.957	.967	.938	.931	.916	.900	.932	.927
	.963	.961	.925	.924	.957	.936	.941	.947	.928
$\hat{\gamma}$.950	.971	.986	.960	.964	.960	.965	.970	.933
	.970	.975	.962	.953	.978	.964	.978	.978	.932
RMSEA – null model	.543	.485	.594	.510	.514	.427	.423	.389	.285
	.544	.480	.584	.502	.522	.441	.414	.378	.283
Latent Correlation between AI and HR Scores	.93	.69	.95	.89	.87	.69	.61	.56	.96
	95% CI	95% CI	95% CI						
	[.79, 1.00]	[.58, .79]	[.90, 1.00]	[.86, .93]	[.77, .98]	[.66, .73]	[.52, .70]	[.51, .61]	[.91, 1.00]

.91	.75	.99	.95	.92	.73	.62	.59	.98
95% CI	95% CI	95% CI	95% CI	95% CI	95% CI	95% CI	95% CI	95% CI
[.78, 1.00]	[.64, .87]	[.94, 1.00]	[.91, .99]	[.80, 1.00]	[.69, .77]	[.50, .75]	[.53, .64]	[.93, 1.00]

Note. Estimates based on *Babbage* model are in the upper rows and those derived from *DaVinci* model are in the lower rows. Maximum likelihood estimation with robust standard errors (MLR) was used. RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation; SRMR = Standardized Root Mean Squared Residual; CFI = Comparative Fit Index; TLI = Tucker-Lewis Index; $\hat{\gamma}$ = Gamma Hat using scaled χ^2 .

*** $p < .001$

Figure 1

Latent correlations between human and machine originality scores derived from the hierarchical model (for the Ocsai scores, the model employed the *DaVinci* scores) with all three AUT tasks loading on a higher-order originality factor in both human and machine scores based on automatically translated responses

Validity of Automated Scoring: The Serial Order Effect

We tested whether machine scores replicate the serial order and be-creative effects, two highly replicable phenomena in the creativity literature. In the case of serial order, we relied on a series of multilevel models. In the “be creative” effect, we used independent samples t-tests. For automatically translated responses, the machine scores were derived from the models incorporating *DaVinci* scores, chosen due to its highest links with human ratings, as reported earlier.

We estimated two models for each prompt to examine the serial order effect for responses’ originality. Our initial models tested if ideas became more original with time while controlling for the assessment type (machine vs. human) and the interaction *Assessment x Order* to discover potentially different patterns among machine and human-based scores (see SOM Table S5 for the specific results). The second model (see Table 4) included the quadratic function of the order to account for curvilinear effects—i.e., the possibility that ideas become more original only up to a certain point, after which their originality stabilizes or declines (Glăveanu et al., 2019). The more complex models controlling for curvilinear links fitted better in all cases (cf. SOM Table S5), as indicated by lower Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), and Deviance statistics. Thus, subsequent ideas became more original than initial ones, yet the originality increased only to a certain point before leveling off (Table 4). After achieving this optimum, originality started to decline. Importantly, in most cases, we did not observe any significant *Assessment x Order* interactions when running more complex models. The significant *Assessment x Order* interactions were found only in the case of alternate uses of a brick (both in Study 1 and Study 2) but were characterized by a small effect size ($\beta = -.08$, 95% CI $[-.16, -.01]$; $\beta = -.13$, 95% CI $[-.18, -.07]$, respectively) suggesting that the differences between human and machine originality scores were negligible. Similarly, the significant *Assessment x Order²* interaction for brick in Study 1 was trivial in terms of effect size ($\beta = .05$, 95% CI $[-.00, .10]$). Therefore, the originality tended to increase and then decrease in precisely the same way, regardless of the source of originality scoring: machine versus human (Figure 2). This attests to automated scoring’s validity.

More discrepancies between automatic and human scores were found when we re-estimated our multilevel, serial-order models on an untranslated input. The *Assessment x Order* interactions were significant in the case of brick, Study 1 ($\beta = -.16$, 95% CI $[-.23, -.08]$), brick, Study 2 ($\beta = -.15$, 95% CI $[-.20, -.10]$), and can ($\beta = -.09$, 95% CI $[-.15, -.04]$). There were also significant *Assessment x Order*² effects for brick, Study 1 ($\beta = .07$, 95% CI $[.02, .12]$), and can ($\beta = .06$, 95% CI $[.03, .09]$). Thus, despite small effect sizes, the dynamic pattern of originality scores tended to differ more systematically for machine and human ratings when non-translated rather than translated input was used.

Table 4

Linear mixed model estimates of the predictors of human and machine originality scores with quadratic terms of serial order included (automatically translated input)

	Study 1				Study 2											
	Brick				Brick				Can				Rope			
Fixed effects	b (SE)	95% CI	t	p	b (SE)	95% CI	t	p	b (SE)	95% CI	t	p	b (SE)	95% CI	t	p
Intercept	0.06 (0.03)	0.00, 0.11	2.00	.046	0.03 (0.02)	-0.02, 0.08	1.10	.271	0.03 (0.03)	-0.02, 0.08	1.15	.249	0.01 (0.02)	-0.03, 0.05	0.53	.597
Assessment	-0.03 (0.03)	-0.09, 0.02	-1.15	.248	-0.02 (0.02)	-0.05, 0.02	-0.81	.420	-0.01 (0.02)	-0.05, 0.03	-0.32	.749	-0.01 (0.02)	-0.05, 0.03	-0.35	.723
Serial order	0.06 (0.01)	0.05, 0.07	8.33	<.001	0.09 (0.01)	0.08, 0.10	13.62	<.001	0.04 (0.01)	0.03, 0.05	6.12	<.001	0.01 (0.01)	-0.01, 0.02	0.67	.500
Serial order ²	-0.02 (0.00)	-0.02, -0.01	-6.51	<.001	-0.01 (0.00)	-0.01, 0.00	-3.61	<.001	-0.01 (0.00)	-0.01, -0.01	-4.61	<.001	-0.01 (0.00)	-0.01, 0.00	-2.66	.008
Assessment × Serial order	-0.02 (0.01)	-0.04, 0.00	-2.29	.022	-0.04 (0.01)	-0.06, -0.03	-4.65	<.001	0.00 (0.01)	-0.02, 0.02	0.26	.794	0.01 (0.01)	-0.01, 0.03	1.35	.179
Assessment × Serial order ²	0.01 (0.00)	0.00, 0.01	2.02	.044	0.01 (0.00)	0.00, 0.01	1.57	.117	0.00 (0.00)	0.00, 0.01	0.65	.514	0.00 (0.00)	0.00, 0.01	0.66	.511
Random effects	Variance		SD		Variance		SD		Variance		SD		Variance		SD	
Participant	.07		.27		.15		.39		.17		.41		.08		.29	
Model Fit																
AIC	3870.96				5137.99				5764.09				5125.03			
BIC	3916.80				5186.66				5812.80				5173.48			
Deviance	3855.00				5122.00				5748.10				5109.00			
ICC	.21				.39				.37				.25			
R ² Marginal	.05				.05				.02				.01			
R ² Conditional	.25				.42				.39				.25			

Notes. *Assessment* is a 2-level categorical variable (human vs. machine scores) with human scores as the reference category. Serial order was person-level centered prior to analyses. *p*-values for fixed effects were calculated using Satterthwaite's approximations. Confidence Intervals [CI] were calculated using the Wald method.

Model equation: $AUT_score \sim assessment * (serial_order + serial_order^2) + (1 | participant)$.

Figure 2

The serial order effect observed in each AUT task as estimated based on human and automated scores (automatically translated input)

The “Be Creative” Effect

Do automated scores also show the “be creative” effect? Note that in Study 2, we randomly assigned participants to “be fluent” or “be creative” conditions. Originality assessed by human raters yielded statistically significant and robust differences, with participants in the “be creative” condition scoring higher than those in the “be fluent” condition, $t(365.92) = 10.01$, $p < .001$, Cohen $d = 1.02$, 95% CI: [0.81, 1.23]. Precisely the same pattern occurred when automated scores were compared, $t(364.01) = 9.89$, $p < .001$, $d = 1.01$, 95% CI: [0.79, 1.22] (see Figure 3).

On untranslated input, we observed a statistically significant “be creative” effect for human ratings, $t(387) = 10.29$, $p < .001$, Cohen $d = 1.05$, 95% CI: [0.83, 1.26] and virtually the same pattern for automatic scores, $t(387) = 10.26$, $p < .001$, $d = 1.04$, 95% CI: [0.83, 1.25].

Figure 3

The “be creative” effect observed across the AUT tasks as estimated based on human and machine scores (automatically translated input)

Note. Plotted are the predicted values of the latent variables—specifically, second-order, person-level originality scores—based on the estimated hierarchical model. These predicted values were generated using the *predict* function in lavaan, and were then individually standardized for both human and AI-based raters to ensure comparability. For the Ocsai scores, the hierarchical model employed the *DaVinci* model size.

Discussion

Scoring DT tasks is by no means an easy task. At a minimum, it requires well-trained, dedicated, and mindful judges. The time and effort of such judges are usually not cheap. In this investigation, we examined the effectiveness of a newly proposed method (Organisciak et al., 2023) to automatically score DT tasks, which—thanks to an openly available platform (Organisciak & Dumas, 2020)—might convince more scholars to focus on divergent thinking in their research. Moreover, we tested to what extent automated and human-provided scores would be comparable if the original language of the collected responses differed from the one in which the models were trained. Our approach was quite straightforward: we automatically translated the DT responses from Polish to English using widely and freely available tools: Microsoft Office Translators or Google Translate engines. We did not control for translation quality or improve it, other than translating parts of responses omitted by the translation program due to specific letters in Polish. Furthermore, we repeated our analyses using Osci scores obtained from untranslated input, which included prompts and responses originally provided by participants in Polish—a language different from the one the model was trained on.

Our results bring observed and latent correlations that many scholars would consider much more than optimistic. Indeed, we believe that the methods recently proposed (Organisciak et al., 2023) and re-examined in this paper, hold the potential to serve as “game changers” in creativity research. Not only did they result in moderate-to-strong correlations at the idea- and prompt level, but when hierarchically modeled at the person level, they were practically indistinguishable from human ratings. Correlations in the nineties are scarcely seen when analyzing the reliability of any psychometric task, not only divergent thinking. But when the correlation coefficient exceeds .95 or so, it seems uncontroversial to conclude that there is a perfect agreement between the sources analyzed.

Although our findings provide a highly encouraging picture, it is also quite nuanced. What seems essential is the heterogeneity of the effects we obtained. Although strong overall, the

correlations differed between studies (Study 1 vs. Study 2), despite using the same prompt (a brick) and across prompts in Study 2. While these differences appear less critical if several tasks are used and modeled together, they might matter when a single task, especially with the atypical prompt, is used. Future tests using various prompts scored by human coders for originality are needed to establish the generalizability of the quality of automated ratings.

Consider, for example, that the links with human ratings observed in this study were systematically lower for rope as a prompt. We attributed this to potential ambiguities in English translation of the Polish word “sznurek”, which led us to consider multiple interpretations, including “string” or “tape”. Notably, different translations might distinctly suggest specific *uses* for an object, which is particularly pertinent in the context of the AUT: for example, in English, a rope is perceived as a thick, strong cord that might be used on ships, for climbing exercises, to tie a noose, etc. Nevertheless, we obtained similar results irrespective of the translation used, and differences persisted even with untranslated input. One potential explanation might lie in the psycholinguistic characteristics of the prompt words used (see, e.g., Forthmann et al., 2016; Ogurlu et al., 2023). Yet, mere word frequency may not be the key differentiating factor here: according to the National Corpus of Polish (<http://nkjp.pl/index.php?page=0&lang=1>), the frequencies per million words are reasonably similar for rope (2.03), brick (2.13), and only slightly lower for can (1.84). Still, other psycholinguistic variables, such as the semantic diversity of the prompt word, could be at play. While these characteristics may primarily influence the idea generation process, particularly fluency, they might also affect the consistency between human and machine scores to some extent. This is an intriguing path for future research into the co-occurrence of human and machine-based judgments in creativity assessment.

Given the exceptionally strong prompt- and person-level aggregated latent correlations between automated and human scores, it might seem obvious that automated ratings will also be valid. Indeed, given that correlation with human raters achieved unity (upper bound of confidence interval), it is hard to find it surprising that both methods followed the same pattern of correlations

and differences when assessed in terms of validity. Still, we emphasize that automated ratings replicated the serial order effect-like pattern, i.e., ideas became more original with time up to a certain point (see also Beaty & Johnson, 2021) and that ideas generated under the “be creative” instruction were scored as much more original by both human raters and AI algorithms. Even the effect size of the differences obtained was the same ($d = 1$). Although future studies should explore other aspects of automated ratings’ validity, e.g., by including well-established correlates of divergent thinking—be it creative self-concept (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019), intelligence (Silvia, 2015) or personality factors (Lebuda et al., 2021)—we treat the results of our validity check initial yet highly encouraging. For further examples of how such validation efforts might unfold, see Dumas, Organisciak, and Doherty (2021) as well as Dumas, Organisciak, Maio, and Doherty (2021), who utilized differences in divergent thinking performance between professional actors and laypeople to build a validity argument for automated originality and elaboration scores, respectively.

Last but not least, we emphasize a high similarity of our findings when automatically translated and untranslated responses were used. Apart from small differences between models (semantic distances were not available for Polish prompts and responses), the overall picture was virtually the same. Not only the person-level correlation between human and automated scores achieved unity, but also the same validity patterns emerged in the case of serial order and “be creative” instruction. The marginal differences observed in the serial order analyses when using untranslated input may in part be attributed to the current limitations of AI-based tools in handling non-English languages. Language models, including Ocsai, are primarily trained on English text. Consequently, even though these models can handle translations, their performance with non-English input might not be as accurate due to the relative scarcity of non-English training data. Thus, translating responses to English (even with the freely available automatic translators used here) might help to mitigate these inconsistencies and improve the alignment between human and machine scores. Nevertheless, given the small effect sizes of these differences, Ocsai appears extremely effective at scoring both automatically translated and untranslated responses.

Limitations and Future Directions

The results of this investigation should be interpreted in light of some limitations. The most prevailing is the procedure we applied, i.e., translating the responses to English instead of training the algorithm to assess the responses provided in Polish. Moreover, we acknowledge that despite the significant advancements in translation systems, they can still sometimes struggle with idioms and other language-specific nuances, thus affecting the observed human-machine correlations. While having the model trained on the original language seems exciting and worthwhile, we believe our approach holds some significant merits. First, it was quick and—as we demonstrated—effective. Second, we were able to capitalize on the benefits of the extensive training Organisciak and colleagues (2023) conducted. Therefore, although we believe that training AI models directly on non-English languages is a natural step forward, we think the approach presented here is remarkably effective for using an English model on other languages. This limitation is additionally softened by the effects obtained in models on untranslated input. Given that they were virtually the same despite the AI model trained in a different language is highly encouraging for broader use of Ocsai.

The second limitation of this study's conclusions stems from the heterogeneity of the correlations obtained. While our hierarchical model demonstrated a perfect correlation between human raters and combined AI and semantic distance scores (or only AI scores in the case of untranslated input), correlations at the idea level with particular AUT prompts varied. This was particularly well illustrated by the case of "sznurek" (rope, string), which resulted in significantly lower correlations between human raters and AI algorithms. Thus, when separate tasks are used, the accuracy of automated scoring might be much lower, mainly when data are analyzed at the level of responses, not prompt-level aggregates. Tasks (and DT prompts) differ in their conceptual space and difficulty; therefore, future studies are necessary to understand this approach's generalizability to other prompts.

Furthermore, lower correlations with human ratings observed for semantic distance-based scores should not discourage further exploration of this method. After all, Ocsai, and large language

models in general, aim to emulate human rating behavior, whereas semantic distance offers a distinct approach to scoring AUT responses. The focus on real-life creative activities and achievements could further help in ensuring the validity of both methods.

Another limitation lies in the relatively short 2-minute timeframe assigned for each prompt in both studies. This could potentially limit the number of ideas generated by the participants and, as a result, affect the serial order patterns observed. The datasets used in this study come from larger research projects, where serial order analyses were not explicitly planned, and the shorter task duration was deemed sufficient for the objectives of those projects. Nevertheless, despite this limitation, we did observe serial order patterns that were consistent across human and machine scores. We expect these patterns to be even more pronounced in studies with longer task duration.

Finally, it should be noted that automated scoring with large language models, like the approach from Organisciak et al. (2023), is very new and still requires investigation into the underlying reasons for its effectiveness. It quite certainly imitates human raters when providing the originality scores for responses, but it will likely also mimic more mundane patterns, such as aligning with the distribution of rating scores that human judges follow. A thorough investigation into the semantic and contextual factors affecting variance in these scores is important work that remains to be done. This becomes even more vital given the recent advances in large learning models, e.g., GPT-4, and a broader discussion regarding the role of AI for and in creativity (Vinchon et al., in press). Nonetheless, recent studies highlighting the efficacy of large language models in analyzing complex psychological constructs (e.g., sentiment or discrete emotions) and handling input from multiple languages (Rathje et al., 2023) offer great promise for future applications. Given our current findings, we would also encourage the use of multiple AI-based scoring methods or multiple model sizes (i.e., Ada, Curie, etc.) in scoring creative products. This approach could mirror the practice of employing multiple human judges and potentially mitigate the limitations inherent to any single automated system. Therefore, in addition to utilizing multiple tasks and modeling them collectively to account for differences in the conceptual space of prompt words, we also suggest integrating scores from

various AI-based models and systems to tackle measurement (i.e., scoring) error even more effectively.

Conclusion

To conclude, the combination of the GPT-3-based AI scoring algorithms with semantic distance scores provides a close-to-perfect prediction of how human judges would score DT tasks. Moreover, the automated ratings are valid: they follow the serial order effect, and ideas generated under the “be creative” condition are indeed more original than those proposed in the “be fluent” condition. The biggest advantage of the current approach seems to be the possibility of using input responses automatically translated into English or even provided in other languages in which the data are originally collected. That makes scoring—usually long and tedious—fast and efficient. We invite fellow creativity researchers to replicate these findings in their languages.

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